

AN INVESTIGATION INTO THE INTERACTION OF TRANSVERSE MATRIX CRACKS AND DELAMINATIONS IN LAMINATED COMPOSITE MATERIALS

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1 Introduction

When composite laminates are loaded above their elastic limit, transverse cracks initiate in the off-axis plies. Upon further loading, these cracks propagate until they reach the ply boundaries, at which point they form micro-delaminations. These micro-delaminations then grow progressively and coalesce to form macroscopic delaminations. The composite material/structure then loses all of its structural integrity, and fails catastrophically.

Advanced three-dimensional finite element damage models are now commonplace to model failure in laminated composite materials and structures. In general, these models treat transverse cracks and delamination as two separate non-interacting damage mechanisms. However, as described above, these damage mechanisms are in fact highly coupled. This paper, thus, sets out to investigate the relationship between transverse cracks and delamination in laminate composite materials.

In order to examine this transverse crack-delamination relationship (coupling), three-point, four-point and four-point offset bending experiments are carried out using a micro-tensile tester housed in the chamber of a scanning electron microscope (SEM), which allows for real-time analysis of the microscopic damage mechanisms, as they initiate and grow. The different bending modes produce different combinations of direct (tension/compression) and shear stresses on the composite beams. A suitable combination of these test results allows for the isolation of specific stresses and the effect of these stresses on the damage progression. The failed beams are subsequently analysed under an SEM to examine the failure surfaces and conclusions are drawn.

2 Problem Description

2.1 Beam Geometries and Material

All testing was carried out using the carbon fibre reinforced polymer, HTA/6376. The test specimens were made using a vacuum assisted autoclave process. Four different laminates were manufactured and tested, which were variations of [90/0/90] and [0/90/0] stacking sequences, as seen in Figure 1. All specimens were 7mm wide, where the width is represented by H . Thickness, T , is dependent on stacking sequence and span length, L , is dependent on test method. The thickness of each ply prior to curing is given as 0.125mm. The coordinate system used is shown in Figure 2.

Fig. 1: Thickness and fibre direction for (A)[90₄/0₇/90₄] and (B)[0₄/90_x/0₄] specimens.

The [90/0/90] specimen is used because the transverse crack growth and development of delaminations were easily tracked with 90° plies on the outer tensile surface of the specimen. Due to the steady growth of the delaminations, these specimens

are ideal for measurement of delamination length as a function of applied load.

Specimens with a [0/90/0] stacking sequence were loaded until significant transverse crack damage was observed. The thickness of the 90° plies was varied to investigate the correlation between the location of transverse cracking and the thickness of the 90° section of the specimens. The [0/90/0] stacking sequence was used in this case as having the stiffer 0° plies on the exterior of the specimen is more representative of what would be used in industry and is therefore highly relevant.

Fig. 2: Coordinate system and general dimensions for specimens.

2.2 Characteristics Studied

The characteristics of delaminations that were studied in this research were as follows:

- The delamination length as a function of applied load for specimens with single or multiple transverse cracks.
- The load levels at which new transverse cracks were initiated.
- The location of transverse cracks across the span length as a function of the thickness of the 90° layer in a [0/90/0] sequenced laminate.

2.3 Test Methods

All testing was conducted using a microtester (Deben Ltd, UK) which provided three- and four-point bending, as well as four-point offset bending facilities, as shown in Figures 3, 4 and 5. The test rig was specially designed to be controlled and carry out tests from outside the SEM. Real-time video footage was recorded during testing to identify failure events. This video footage was then correlated with the load-displacement data received from the mechanical tester. From this data, the effects of the stress state on the failure of the specimen was then interpreted.

2.3.1 Three-Point Bending

Figure 3 shows the geometry for the span length used during three-point bending. Pins of 5mm diameter with 8mm diameter lubricated bushings were used to reduce frictional effects in all tests conducted. The diameter of the loading pins do not have a strong influence on test results, once bearing damage is avoided from particularly small diameter pins [1]. The bending moment (BM) is represented by the hatched pattern on the specimens in Figures 3, 4 and 5. Maximum normal stress due to bending occurs at the centre of the span length at the loading pin. Normal stresses are zero at the outer support pins. Maximum tensile stress is on the surface furthest from the loading pin, and maximum compressive stress is on the surface touching the pin. Due to the contact with the loading pin, there are additional stress concentrations associated with this location. The interlaminar shear stress is constant across the span length of the specimen, varying parabolically across the thickness, peaking at the neutral axis.

Fig. 3: Three-point bending moment variation across span length. Distances between pins also shown.

2.3.2 Four-Point Bending

Figure 4 shows the geometry for the span length tested in four-point bending. The bending moment, which is at zero at each of the support pins, reaches a maximum between the loading pins and is constant in this section of the span length. Interlaminar shear stress exists only in the outer quarters of the span length, between the left and right sets of load and support pins.

Fig. 4: Four-point bending moment variation across span length. Distances between pins also shown

2.3.3 Four-Point Offset Bending

The case of the stress state in four-point offset bending is nearly the exact opposite of that for regular four-point bending. At the centre of the span length seen in Figure 5, the bending moment is zero, and the interlaminar shear stress is at a constant maximum between the two central opposing pins. Failure in this region is attributed to shear stress. The results of four-point offset bend tests were used in conjunction with equations 1 - 4 to calculate the interlaminar shear stress associated with the maximum load prior to failure of specimens.

Fig. 5: Four-point offset bending moment variation across span length. Distances between pins also shown.

3 Theoretical Analysis

3.1 Maximum Bending Moment

The following equation is used when calculating the maximum bending moment in

Three-point flexure:

$$BM_{max} = \frac{PL}{4} \quad (1)$$

Four-point flexure:

$$BM_{max} = \frac{P(L - L_1)}{4} \quad (2)$$

For the crosshead geometry used in this study a higher load is required in four-point bending when compared to three-point bending to achieve comparable shear and normal stresses. The negative side effects of this relationship is discussed later.

3.2 Local Delamination Ratio

The local delamination ratio, τ_{LDR} , can be calculated by measuring the lengths of delaminations under SEM [2]. The local delamination ratio is then plotted against the force applied, and repeated for various different load levels.

$$\tau_{LDR} = \frac{e}{H_1} \quad (3)$$

Where e is the length of the delamination to one side of the transverse crack and H_1 is the thickness of the 90° section of a laminate following a [90/0/90] stacking sequence. This can be seen in Figure 6.

Fig. 6: Local delamination ratio of a [90/0/90] stacked specimen.

3.3 Interlaminar Shear Stress

For three-point bending of short beams and offset four-point bending Equation 4 from classical beam theory can be used to calculate the interlaminar shear stress of unidirectional composite materials [3,4,5].

$$\tau_{uni} = \frac{3P}{4TH} \quad (4)$$

where P is the load applied.

However, none of the specimens tested for this paper were unidirectional laminates. Interlaminar shear stress of heterogeneous beams can be calculated once a correction factor, β , has been applied [3,5]. β takes the thickness of the 0° and 90° plies into consideration (see Figure 7) when calculating interlaminar shear stress by

$$\tau_{multi} = \frac{3P}{4TH}\beta \quad (5)$$

where

$$\beta = \frac{1 + k^2(n - 1)}{1 + k^3(n - 1)} \quad (6)$$

and from Figure 7

$$k = \frac{h_1}{h_2} \quad (7)$$

and

$$n = \frac{E_1}{E_2} \quad (8)$$

Where E_1 and E_2 are 140GPa and 10GPa, respectively, for HTA/6376 [6].

Fig. 7: Ratio of ply thicknesses, to be used when determining correction factor, k , for shear stress calculation.

4 Results

The results from three- and four-point, as well as offset bending are addressed separately.

4.1 Three Point Bending

4.1.1 Transverse Crack and Delamination Development

In all stacking sequences tested, failure generally occurred at the centre of the span length, at the central loading pin of the three-point bending apparatus. Examples of this can be seen in Figure 8.

Fig. 8: Failure in Three-Point Bending for (A) $[90_4/0_7/90_4]$, (B) $[0_4/90_7/0_4]$, and (C) $[0_4/90_3/0_4]$.

In the $[90_4/0_7/90_4]$ specimens under three-point bending, a number of locations along the span length can be identified during testing at which microcrack growth can be observed (Figure 9(A)). Generally, only a single transverse crack fully develops from this. While testing, it was observed that microcrack growth occurred very gradually. The coalescence of these microcracks and full transverse crack (Figure 9(B)) development was an almost instant process. When delamination follows (Figure 9(C)), it was observed to be a steady process with no sudden changes but gradual separation between the plies (Figure 9(D)) as load continued to increase.

AN INVESTIGATION INTO DELAMINATION CRACKS AT PLY BOUNDARIES DUE TO MATRIX CRACKING IN TRANSVERSE PLIES

Fig. 9: A - D, Stages of Failure in a [90/0/90] stacked laminate. (A) Microcracking, (B) transverse cracking, (C) delamination and (D) catastrophic failure are shown.

In Figure 10A-E, all images were focused on the same region of the [0₄/90₇/0₄] specimen during testing and the mechanics of the delamination can be observed. The failure of the bond between fibre and matrix as delamination occurs is between 263N – 305N. The series of images show the development of cusps [7] associated with failure involving shear stress.

Fig. 10: A - E, Stages of Delamination. (A) 263N, (B) 285N, (C) 290N, (D) 295N and (E) 305N. Crescent shaped voids are shown growing into delaminations, with visible cusps.

While testing specimens with 0° on the exterior, such as the [0₄/90₇/0₄] specimen seen in Figure 11, there was very little indication, if any, of microcrack growth prior to sudden catastrophic delamination.

Fig. 11: Z-Shaped Delamination Path in a [0/90/0] stacked specimen. Crack path follows ply boundary closest to loading/support pins.

Figure 11 shows the typical type of failure associated with specimens tested with the 0° plies on the exterior. Transverse cracking and delamination occur suddenly and simultaneously, following a Z-shaped path (highlighted in Figure 11 in white). It was noted in both three- and four-point bending of these specimens that the delamination occurred on the ply boundary between the 0° and 90° plies closest to the pins.

4.1.2 Three-Point Delamination Lengths

The load and displacement data for the specimens tested in three-point bending can be seen in Figure 12.

Fig. 12: Three-point bending, load – displacement data for all specimens tested.

Delaminations to the left and the right of the transverse crack (TC), seen in Figure 13 were measured at various load levels. Figure 14 shows the length of the delaminations on either side of the main transverse crack in two different [90₄/0₇/90₄] specimens, similar to what is seen in the SEM image of Figure 9(C).

Fig. 13: Delamination length left and right of TC in a [90/0/90] stacked specimen.

The black markers on Figure 14 are from a specimen with one transverse crack. The white markers are from a specimen which developed a number of transverse cracks, but only the lengths of the delamination at the centre of bending were measured.

Fig. 14: Measurement of delamination lengths either side of a transverse crack in two different [90₄/0₇/90₄] specimens. Black markers for specimen with a single TC, white markers for specimen with multiple TCs.

4.2 Four-Point Bending

4.2.1 Transverse Crack Location along Span

Catastrophic failure in four-point bending occurred in different locations along the span length of the specimen depending on stacking sequence. Figure 15 highlights the location of failure in four samples, one from each variety of stacking sequence tested.

Fig. 15: Transverse cracking in (A) [90₄/0₇/90₄], (B) [0₄/90₁₁/0₄], (C) [0₄/90₃/0₄] and (D) [0₄/90₇/0₄].

The locations of the centre point of the transverse crack on [0/90/0] stacked specimens was measured with reference to the closest support pin which varied from left to right depending on the particular specimen, illustrated in Figure 16. These measurements have been compiled in Figure 17 for

the various $[0/90/0]$ specimens tested and plotted against the thickness of the 90° plies.

Fig. 16: Transverse crack location in a $[0/90/0]$ specimen. Location given relative to loading and support pins.

Fig. 17: Measurement of transverse crack location with varying thickness of 90° plies.

All load and displacement data for specimens tested in four-point bending can be seen in Figure 18. As with the three-point bending test results, each different stacking sequence tested is visually distinct due to the variations in stiffness between specimens tested.

4.2.2 Four-Point Delamination Length

Fig. 18: Four-point bending, load – displacement data for all specimens tested.

Figure 19 indicates the load levels for three $[90_4/0/90_4]$ specimens at which a transverse crack occurs. The hatched portion at the bottom of each bar indicates the range of loading values for which there were no transverse cracks. The top of each bar is the load level at which the specimens failed. Each horizontal line indicates the initiation of a new transverse crack as load is increased, observed using the SEM.

Fig. 19: Transverse crack initiation loads, and ultimate failure loads for three $[90/0/90]$ specimens.

Specimens of stacking sequence $[90_4/0_7/90_4]$ are used to measure the length of delamination as a function of load. A number of different transverse cracks (seen in Figure 20) developed delaminations between the loading pins of the four-point bending crossheads. Similar to Figure 14, these are measured to the left and right of the contributing transverse crack and can be seen in Figure 20 and Figure 21.

Fig. 20: Delamination lengths to left of multiple TCs in a $[90/0/90]$ specimen.

Fig. 21: Delamination Lengths to right of multiple TCs in a $[90/0/90]$ specimen.

4.3 Four-Point Offset Bending

Four-point offset bending was carried out in order to establish a value for the interlaminar shear strength of the materials tested in the standard three- and four-point flexural tests seen previously. Specimens of $[0_4/90_{11}/0_4]$ (Figure 22(A)), $[0_4/90_7/0_4]$ (Figure 22(B)) and $[0_4/90_3/0_4]$ (Figure 22(C)) were tested and all exhibited very similar failure modes. Transverse

cracks developed in all specimens at the centre of the span length, between the two inner loading pins.

Fig. 22: Specimens (A) $[0_4/90_{11}/0_4]$, (B) $[0_4/90_7/0_4]$ and (C) $[0_4/90_3/0_4]$ after failure during interlaminar shear tests, under four-point offset bending. Transverse crack location is highlighted in images.

4.3.1 Interlaminar Shear Stress

The load displacement data for four-point offset bending can be seen in Figure 23.

Fig. 23: Four-point offset bending, load – displacement data for $[0/90/0]$ stacked laminates with varying thicknesses of 90° plies.

Using the method outlined from Equation 4 – 8, the interlaminar shear strength was calculated. Results are seen in Table 1.

Table 1: Interlaminar Shear Strength

Stacking Sequence	τ_{multi} (MPa)
[0 ₄ /90 ₃ /0 ₄]	16.06
[0 ₄ /90 ₇ /0 ₄]	16.48
[0 ₄ /90 ₁₁ /0 ₄]	21.22

4.3.2 Surface Analysis

After Failure of the [0₄/90₁₁/0₄] specimen in four-point offset bending, it was peeled apart to expose the surfaces separated by delamination during testing. A macroscopic view of the separated specimen can be seen in Figure 24.

Fig. 24: Top and side elevations of specimen after failure in four-point offset bending with annotations for SEM images.

Element A, seen in Figure 25, shows the surface of the slanted edge of the transverse crack. This surface was angled at approximately 45°. This surface which failed under shear dominated failure is visually distinct from the failure surfaces in Figures 26 and 27 due to the presence of debris.

Fig. 25: Element A - Shearing surface showing fibres in the 90° region of the test specimen with debris after separation.

Element B, seen in Figure 26, shows the surface of the 0° ply which was involved in the delamination. This surface is relatively devoid of matrix, aside from the cusps which are evident.

Fig. 26: Element B - Lower surface with fibres very clearly visible with very little debris remaining on neat surfaces.

Element C, seen in Figure 27, shows the surface of the 90° ply which was involved in the delamination.

Fig. 27: Element C - Upper surface showing matrix material and very clear imprints of where fibres were pulled away from.

5 Discussion

In three-point bending, failure generally occurred at the centre of the span length of the specimen. This is due to the coinciding of maximum shear stress and direct stress due to bending at this location. Microcrack growth in the $[90_4/0_7/90_4]$ specimens was relatively slow and steady with increasing load, prior to sudden transverse crack growth. The gradual crack opening which separated fibres and matrix, with eventual failure of resin bridges connecting fibres leading to ultimate failure which was observed during testing is very similar to descriptions of similar failure seen in previous research [8].

When the transverse crack reaches the ply boundary, it is shown in Figure 10 that delamination in three-point bending is a steady process, where there is an almost linear increase in delamination length relative to applied load. Figure 14 shows two of the same type of specimen, $[90_4/0_7/90_4]$, however the delamination lengths of one of these specimens (white markers) is significantly lower than the other specimens (black markers). This is due to that particular specimen having a number of transverse cracks and delaminations along its span length. In the specimen with the single transverse crack, the delamination is focused at the centre of curvature. Delamination lengths of both specimens tested showed a relatively linear response to load increase. The delamination lengths were presented in terms of τ_{LDR} which will allow for appropriate comparison with specimens of varying 90° ply thicknesses.

In four-point bending, there were typically 5 or 6 transverse cracks in $[90_4/0_7/90_4]$ specimens tested prior to ultimate failure. Figure 19 shows where the initiation loads for transverse cracks were recorded. It can be noted from Figure 19 that there is a relatively steady increase in the number of transverse cracks from the first to ultimate failure as load is increased. Ultimate failure in these specimens occurred when the delamination from one transverse crack met an opposing delamination from an alternative transverse crack. This resulted in an immediate decrease in the stiffness of the material.

Failure in the $[90_4/0_7/90_4]$ specimens was observed in the region of constant maximum tensile stress between the two loading pins. However, failure in the alternative style of stacking sequence, $[0/90/0]$, occurred beyond this region, in the quarters of the span length between the loading pin and support pin. This is the region of maximum shear stress in four-point bending. Failure in this region was characterised by a sudden transverse crack and delamination which occurred simultaneously with no obvious indication that failure was approaching. It can be seen in Figure 11 that with this type of transverse failure at the core of a specimen, the delamination develops in a z-shaped path. The path followed the boundary of alternately orientated plies swapping from tensile to compressive sides of the neutral axis to remain close to the nearest loading or support pin. Transverse failure in this region is shear stress dominated.

The location of the transverse crack relative to the nearest support pin was measured. This distance was then plotted against the number of 90° plies at the core of the $[0/90/0]$ specimens in Figure 17. It is plotted in terms of A/B so as to allow for comparison with similar analyses with varying distances between loading and support pins. It is indicated from this chart that the linear increase in thickness of the 90° portion of the specimen, resulted in a linear increase in distance from the outer support pin. It was observed that the thinnest specimens failed closer to the outer support pin, and with increasing thickness this transverse failure approached the nearest loading pin. This is most likely an effect of local stress concentrations due to the pin diameters and span length of the beam which will be investigated further in future work. It was noted during testing that the fewer the number of 90° plies in the $[0/90/0]$ sequenced specimens, the more difficult it is to induce

transverse crack failure, and alternative failure modes are often observed. For example, $[0_4/90_3/0_4]$ nearly always failed at the loading pin in the 0° plies by compression and buckling. It was found in the $[0_4/90_7/0_4]$ specimens, that failure could be encouraged to occur due to a transverse cracking in the 90° plies by reducing the rate at which the displacement was applied to the specimen.

It is suggested from Equations 1 and 2 that the increased likelihood of failure due to compression and buckling at the pins in four-point bending is as a result of the differences in geometry of the three- and four-point bending crossheads, in particular the lengths L and L_1 . From Equations 1 and 2 it was determined that the ratio of the bending moment induced for a particular load applied for three- and four-point bending was 14:15. This means that to induce an equivalent bending moment, for every 14N applied in three point bending, 15N is to be applied in four-point bending. Although the bending moments are the same, the stress concentration factor between the specimen and the loading pin has a greater role to play in failure due to the increased load required, leading to the compressive buckling failure at the pins. In four-point bending, the lengths of the delaminations were measured from all transverse crack locations. With the constant bending moment between the two loading pins it was indicated that there was a linear increase in delamination length with load applied, independent of where across L_1 the transverse crack was located.

It was determined in four-point bending that in many of the specimens of $[0/90/0]$ stacking sequence, excessive interlaminar shear stress was the leading contributor to specimen failure. This was determined from the location of failure, being outside of the region of maximum normal stresses, but in the region under the influence of interlaminar shear stress.

The four-point offset bend tests were carried out to determine the interlaminar shear strengths of the various stacking sequences. All specimens tested failed in the region between the two central loading pins. This region is subjected to pure shear stress with no bending moment to provide normal stresses. This allows for the interlaminar shear strength of the material to be determined for the various stacking sequences.

The two different sides of the delamination in four-point offset bending were separated and this allowed for SEM visual inspection of these surfaces. Figures

26 and 27 show the fibre dominated and matrix dominated faces of the specimen. It can be seen that there is very little contamination or bridging between the two surface types in these two regions which were peeled under mode-I dominated failure. The fibres, and the imprints of the fibres on the opposing matrix dominated surface are well defined. It has been suggested that if bare fibres are very easily observed after failure that there is a poor fibre matrix interface strength [7]. Failure of this nature is attributed to adhesive interfacial failure [8]. The blunt appearance of the cusps seen in Figure 26 indicate a relatively ductile matrix [7]. Figure 25 shows the slanted surface of the transverse crack. By comparison there are very distinct differences to be seen between this surface which failed under shear, and the other surfaces which were mode-I dominated. There is much more matrix debris associated with this surface. The fibres are not continuous and appear to have been sheared during failure.

6 Conclusions

From this preliminary series of tests it can be seen that in three- and four-point flexural testing once a transverse crack has reached an opposing ply boundary, the length of the delamination which follows is proportional to the load applied.

It was observed during testing that in three-point bending, specimens with multiple transverse cracks had significantly shorter delamination lengths. It is proposed that the sum of the length of the multiple delaminations may be equivalent to the longer delamination of a specimen with a single transverse crack. Future work will include further measurement of delamination lengths, particularly in specimens with multiple transverse cracks.

Transverse crack initiation loads were observed during testing. In specimens with multiple transverse cracks it was shown that the specimens which developed transverse cracks earlier also submitted to catastrophic failure at a lower load level. Subsequent transverse cracks occurred at relatively regular intervals, with an atypically large interval prior to catastrophic failure.

It has been shown in specimens which follow a $[0/90/0]$ stacking sequence that the location of the transverse crack through the 90° portion varies depending on the thickness of the 90° portion. Future work will involve determining if this is a material characteristic of altering the stacking sequence, or if

this response is a result related to the geometry of the microtester. The delamination which resulted from these transverse cracks followed a route at the $0^\circ/90^\circ$ ply boundary which kept the delamination as close to the loading or support pins. This is due to the stress concentrations associated with the pins in contact with the surface of the specimens.

Failure in four-point offset bending occurred at the very centre of the span length. This region is subjected to pure shear stress and from this the interlaminar shear strength of the material being tested could be determined. From SEM, the failure surface associated with shear failure was observed to be distinct from the other regions which were associated with mode-I dominated failure.

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